

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA'LIM,
FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
FARG'ONA DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI
IJTIMOIY ISH KAFEDRASI

**"UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARIDA OILA, MAKTAB
VA JAMOATCHILIK HAMKORLIGINI
TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA
IJTIMOIY ISH KASBining AHAMIYATI"** (FALSAFA
FANLARI DOKTORI, PROFESSOR FARXODJON
TURG'UNBOYEVNING YORQIN XOTIRASIGA
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**Mavzusidagi Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya
materiallari to'plami**

2024-yil 30-may

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UDK: 340.347 (575.1)

“Umumta'lim maktablarida oila, maktab va jamoatchilik hamkorligini takomillashtirishda ijtimoiy ish kasbining ahamiyati” mavzusidagi Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari to'plami / Nashrga tayyorlovchilar: B.Tolibov, M.Abduraxmonova, K.Xonkeldiyeva, / Farg'ona davlat universiteti Ijtimoiy ish kafedrası. – Farg'ona., 2024. 579 b.

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Ushbu “Umumta'lim maktablarida oila, maktab va jamoatchilik hamkorligini takomillashtirishda ijtimoiy ish kasbining ahamiyati” mavzusidagi Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari to'plamida O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida ijtimoiy ish kasbiy faoliyatini shakllantirish mexanizmlarini o'rganish, mamlakatimizda kam ta'minlangan oilalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimi samaradorligini oshirish, O'zbekiston umumiy o'rta ta'lim tizimida ijtimoiy ish kasbiy faoliyatini shakllantirish yo'nalishlari kengaytirish, fuqarolarni o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlarida axoli bilan keys menejment asosidagi ijtimoiy ish faoliyatini tashkil etishni tadqiq etish, mamlakatimizda ijtimoiy sohalar iqtisodiyotini tashkil etish va amalga oshirishning dolzarb muammolari bo'yicha maqolalar o'rin olgan.

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OVERCOMING LANGUAGE INTERFERENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT HIGHER EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENTS

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Abstract: The article discusses ways to overcome language interference in teaching English in higher educational establishments. In this work, the term "interference" refers only to the phenomena of the interlinguistic plan, the intralinguistic transfer is interpreted like overgeneralization.

Keywords: ways to overcome, language interference, master the English, speech norm, influence of language, social demand.

A distinctive feature of a modern specialist is the knowledge of a foreign language, which allows him to have a competitive advantage in the labor market. Currently, one of the most common foreign languages is English, which is due to both geopolitical and purely economic reasons. The need to satisfy the social demand for learning English has led to the emergence of a wide network of educational institutions of additional education that provide an opportunity to learn English. The author's experience in such institutions shows that adult students have a sufficient level of motivation to master the English language.

They clearly understand the purpose of learning English. Secondly, training in institutions of additional education is carried out on a paid basis, which requires students to take a responsible approach to the educational process. At the same time, one of the barriers for adults to learn English, which makes the task of overcoming language interference in the process of teaching adults English especially relevant.

It analyzes ways to overcome language interference in the process of teaching adults English in the system of additional education. Starting to study English, adult students already have a certain set of knowledge about the language. Often this knowledge "comes into conflict" with the norms and principles of the functioning of the language being studied. In this case, the phenomenon of linguistic interference mentioned above arises. It must be said that this phenomenon has become the object of research by scientists in various branches of scientific knowledge. So, in psychology, interference is understood as an inhibitory interaction of skills, in which already established skills make it difficult to form new ones or reduce their effectiveness.

Despite a significant number of definitions of the concept of "language interference", researchers agree that language interference is a deviation from the speech norm of the second language that occurs under the influence of the first language. So, A. S. Krutoberezhskaya considers linguistic interference as "... cases of deviation from the speech norm that occur in the speech of a bilingual in a

second (foreign) language under the influence of the first language”. In our opinion, language interference should be understood as the result of the mixing of language codes that occurs in the speech activity of students and affects the process of learning English. The experience of teaching English made it possible to determine the factors of the occurrence of language interference, which include:

- the influence of the native language of the listeners;
- the influence of a second foreign language (often students studying in the system of additional education study a second foreign language or studied another foreign language at school);
- socio-political, economic and cultural changes;
- development of scientific thought;
- availability of different standards of English.

Mastering the English language involves studying the culture of English-speaking countries. As rightly noted by V.S. Vinogradov, culture is a set of material and spiritual values accumulated and accumulated by a certain community of people, and those values of one national community that are completely absent from another or differ significantly from them constitute a national sociocultural

fund that requires study in the process of learning a foreign language. Accordingly, we believe that language interference has the following structure:

- phonetic interference (mixing the rules of phonetics of the English language and the rules of the native or first foreign language)
- grammatical interference (replacement of the rules and features of the morphology of the English language by the rules of another language);
- lexical interference (representation of the studied concept by means of native or first foreign language);
- cultural interference (explaining the phenomena of English culture through familiar cultural stereotypes). Determining how to overcome language interference requires an understanding of what underlies the interference. Phonetic interference, in our opinion, is dictated by the following differences in the native and English languages:

1) the presence in English of different types of stressed syllable, which leads to a difference in the reading of vowels;

2) discrepancy between the rules for the formation of syllables and division into syllables in Uzbek and English;

3) the presence of diphthongs and digraphs in the English language, the influence of the “environment” on reading;

4) the rules for setting stress in polysyllabic words;

5) the presence in the English language of different intonation tones. Starting to learn English, adult students experience some tightness, which is dictated by the

fear of making a mistake and appearing ignorant in the eyes of other students. As rightly stated by P. Ur, the goal of teaching pronunciation is to achieve such a level of foreign language pronunciation that would allow students to successfully communicate in a foreign language.

The use of jokes and funny situations from the learning experience of the teacher himself or other people can help to remove the described psychological barrier. In this regard, it is important that the teacher does not use his students as a "model". The experience of teaching English to adult students has shown that phonetic differences are most firmly fixed by building associative connections by students, turning to associative thinking of students.

Accordingly, in working with students, we practice creative phonetic tasks. When working in pairs, students should make up dialogues containing the studied phonetic material. Another type of task is the compilation of a story, when each of the students must come up with a continuation of the story, and the sentence must include the studied phonetic material. As a rule, such tasks are positively perceived by students and contribute to better assimilation of the material. Thus, the ways to overcome the language interference of adult learners are:

- the use of jokes or funny situations from teaching experience in the educational process;
- establishment of associative links between the phoneme, its graphic presentations and pronunciation;
- the use of creative phonetic tasks. Grammar is an integral part of teaching a foreign language.

Based on the experience of teaching English in the system of additional education, we can conclude that the greatest difficulties for adult students are precisely the study of the grammatical features of the English language. We see the reason for this in significant differences in the grammatical structure of the native and English languages (the presence in the English language of articles, linking verbs, temporary forms, etc.).

According to L.P. Kashirina, the potential of algorithms in teaching the grammar of a foreign language is due to the possibility of reducing grammar to a finite set of rules [6, p. 46]. It is important that students also act as active participants in the compilation of the algorithm, and not just "consumers of knowledge". Visualization of the grammatical phenomenon through the use of pictures or dramatization and working out the material on small educational forms, that is, small texts containing the studied grammatical phenomenon, also act as a presentation and consolidation of grammatical material.

Summing up what has been said, we venture to suggest that overcoming the language interference of adult students in the process of teaching English grammar can be facilitated by:

- algorithmization of grammatical material;
- visualization of the studied grammatical phenomenon;
- working out of grammatical material on small educational texts, drill exercises.

The basis of lexical interference is the use of the native language, dictated by the small vocabulary of students and the presence of "false friends of the translator" / paronyms. The key to overcoming lexical interference is the expansion of the vocabulary of adult learners in English. Based on our own experience of teaching English in the system of additional education, we can say that the most effective methods for introducing new vocabulary were the illustrative method and the descriptive method. Students were asked to correlate the lexeme with the image or think about what associations the word / phrase evokes.

The problem of "false friends of the translator" was often solved by translating sentences and determining the essence of the lexeme through the study of the context. Thus, the meaning of the lexeme „intelligent“ was understood by the students who studied under the Headway Elementary program by translating sentences with this word into Russian and correlating the translation of this lexeme with the context. Possible ways to overcome lexical interference in teaching English to adults, in our opinion, are:

- visualization of the lexeme;
- establishment of associative links between the lexeme and its description;
- correlation of the studied lexeme with the context of the statement.

Syntactic interference is based on the transfer of the sentence construction model from the native language / first foreign language to English. At the initial stage, it is advisable to overcome syntactic interference by preparing algorithms that reflect the features of the syntactic connection (word order) in different types of English sentences. Exercises to develop skills can also be called effective in the learning process - the so-called drill exercises.

Of course, the material of the article does not exhaust all aspects of the problem under study. We see the prospects for scientific research in the development of modern teaching materials for teaching English to adults in institutions of additional education.

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